

THE IMPORTANCE OF QUALITY EDUCATION IN THE PRESENT DAY

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to illustrate how crucial it is for higher institutions to produce qualified graduates who satisfy market demand and possess the necessary credentials, making them employable and best suited for the job, and try to analyze problems and solutions of quality education.

Keywords: *Innovative technologies, high-quality education, sustainability, problem, solution.*

Time evolves from generation to generation, changing not just society but also people’s daily lives, culture, and way of life. In the twenty-first century, when scientific discoveries and the most cutting-edge technologies form the foundation of trade, new ideas, and technologies are prompted by the passage of time. It is clear that as time passes, complexity increases and the necessity for education appropriate for the era in which we live increases. Education must be of a specific quality to suit the requirements of the market, as demonstrated by the change in the teaching methods provided by educational institutions and the use of technology in these settings. As a result, it is important to provide tertiary students with excellent training and equipment to achieve sustainability. Education is the most powerful ability that you can use to change the world and enlighten yourself. of course

A quality education equips students with the ability to interpret things correctly and apply what they have learned. Information in real-life scenarios. A quality

education includes the following aspects: learning resource technology, program registration, modules completed, teaching methods, facilities, qualifications, extracurricular activities, and performance awards, students and faculty also have a unique perspective on institutional management. Education Opinion and Evaluation (Hammond, 2013). Over the years the university has exploded institutions, with up to 13 higher education institutions in Francistown these days. (Miklas, 1977). The purpose of education has always been and will be to enable and impart skills. Since learners know, it is important that the training they receive must be of a certain quality. The quality of education is crucial because what a person learns influences their philosophical "mindset." Hence, stating that one's education has an impact on their everyday life, illustrating their way of life and the decisions one makes daily ("Education for Sustainability: Quality Education Is A Necessity in Modern Day. How Far do the Educational Institutions Facilitate Quality Education?". Journal of Education and Practice. Vol.7, No 2, 2016)

Yet, delivering quality is difficult due to resource limitations such as unstable finances, high costs, lack of time, and devotion. The knowledge of the requirements for providing brand-standard, high-quality education may also be the key issue. Several obstacles prevent poor kids from getting an education. Some are more subtly stated, such as not having a school to attend. like the school's instructor not having the education required to aid youngsters in learning properly. There are some main reasons for the lack of education:

A lack of funding for education; Girls attend a UNRWA day school in Gaza City on August 29, 2018. Hundreds of thousands of Palestinian children are starting school in the Gaza Strip amid a major budget crisis for UN agencies. school.

Girls attending her UNRWA school in her first year in Gaza City, August 29, 2018. Hundreds of thousands of Palestinian children are starting the new school year in Gaza amid a major budget crisis for the UN agency that funds many schools.

Developing countries cannot rely solely on their education funding. We also need foreign aid. According to the Global Partnership for Education (GPE), only 20% of his

education aid goes to low-income countries. But her 13 years of education in a developing country would cost him an average of \$1.25 per day per child.

Having no teachers, or having untrained teachers; There are not enough teachers to achieve universal primary or secondary education. And many of the teachers working today are untrained. As a result, children do not receive a proper education. There are 130 million children in school who are not learning basic skills such as reading, writing, and arithmetic. (<https://www.globalcitizen.org/en/content/10-barriers-to-education-around-the-world-2/>)

No classroom, and a lack of learning materials; Children cannot learn without the right environment. Children in many countries of sub-Saharan Africa are often crammed into overcrowded or collapsing classrooms or learning outdoors. They also lack textbooks, school supplies, and other tools they need to excel. Outdated and worn textbooks are often shared by six or more students in many parts of the world. For example, in Tanzania, only 3.5% of her students in grade 6 used only reading textbooks. In Cameroon, there are 11 pupils per reading textbook and 13 pupils per mathematics textbook in the second grade of primary school. Workbooks, practice sheets, textbooks, and other key materials to help students learn the lessons are lacking. Teachers also need materials to prepare for classes, share with students, and lead classes.

The exclusion of children with disabilities; Students with disabilities have lower attendance rates and are more likely to drop out or drop out before completing primary school. They are more than twice as likely to be suspended or expelled from school than their peers without special education.

A combination of discrimination, lack of teacher training in inclusive education practices, and lack of accessible schools make this group vulnerable to denial of their right to education.

Distance from home to school; Commutes of up to three hours each way are not uncommon for many children around the world. This is simply too much for many children, especially those living with disabilities, malnourished children, sick children,

or children who have to do household chores. Imagine leaving school hungry at times and only coming back at 7 pm. Many children, especially girls, face violence on the long and dangerous journey to and from school.

Living in a country in conflict or at risk of conflict; Every war causes many casualties and the education system is often destroyed. Children exposed to violence are more likely to perform poorly and drop out of school. The impact of conflict is immeasurable. About 250 million children live in conflict-affected countries. Her more than 75 million children and young people from 3 years old to 18 years old in her 35 crisis-affected countries are now in dire need of educational assistance.

The expense of education; The Universal Declaration of Human Rights makes clear that every child has the right to free primary education. In many developing countries, governments have announced the abolition of school fees over the past decades, resulting in a large increase in the number of children attending school. There are effective ways, despite the different problems of getting a quality education. Some of them are mentioned below: maintained infrastructure: Schools should motivate students to come to school by providing the basic amenities required by the standards. Spacious classrooms with furniture, blackboards, electrical equipment, clean and sanitary restrooms, activity and play areas, laboratories, and computer labs are required. Pedagogy skills: Here we need to implement the concept of learning, unlearning, and relearning. It requires a shift from memorization to a conceptual method in which teachers and students can be involved. Quality of teachers: Most schools are downgraded by hiring teachers at low wages. Teachers are an important part of the classroom, inspiring children's minds to seek knowledge. The quality of teachers should be improved by providing training and providing modern materials, tools, and methods such as smart classrooms and digital courses. The next one is extra-curricular activities: Putting pressure on students can distract them from their studies and affect their pursuit of research. Schools should participate in a variety of extra-curricular activities that serve as a key factor in keeping students engaged in school. Improving the quality of education in schools creates an environment that consolidates

the concept of lifelong learning. Students stay in school, learn, and become empowered and productive so they can participate in nation-building. ([HTTP/7-measures-you-should-take-to-improve-the-quality-of-education-in-your-school/](http://7-measures-you-should-take-to-improve-the-quality-of-education-in-your-school/))

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